

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Development and Validation of FTIR Method for Telmisartan-Hydrochlorothiazide Tablets

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 18 Mar 2026

Keywords:

FTIR spectrophotometer;
Telmisartan;
Hydrochlorothiazide;
Method validation;
Quantitative analysis; KBr
pellet method; Tablet dosage
form; Accuracy; Precision;
%RSD

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.19104650

ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid, and reliable Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrophotometric method was developed and validated for the quantitative estimation of telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide in combined tablet dosage form using a solid sampling technique. Standard drugs were analyzed by the KBr pellet method, and characteristic absorption peaks were identified for functional group confirmation. Telmisartan exhibited prominent peaks at 1695.45 cm^{-1} (C=O), 3387.00 cm^{-1} (O-H), and 3637.75 cm^{-1} (N-H). Hydrochlorothiazide showed characteristic peaks at 3637.75 cm^{-1} (N-H), 1327.03 cm^{-1} (SO₂ asymmetric stretching), and 1165.00 cm^{-1} (SO₂ symmetric stretching). The marketed formulation (Telma H) was successfully analyzed using the developed method. The average recovery was found to be 100% of the labeled claim, and the %RSD values ranged between 0.10–0.97%, indicating excellent precision and accuracy. The method was validated for key parameters and found suitable for routine quality control analysis of telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide in tablet dosage forms.

INTRODUCTION

TELMISARTAN

Telmisartan is a non-peptide antihypertensive drug belonging to the class of angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs). It selectively antagonizes the binding of angiotensin II to the AT1 receptor in vascular smooth muscle and the adrenal gland, resulting in vasodilation, reduced aldosterone

secretion, decreased sodium and water reabsorption, and a subsequent reduction in arterial blood pressure.

Chemical formula: C₃₃H₃₀N₄O₂

Molecular weight: 514.6g/mol

IUPAC Name: 2-[4-[[4-methyl-6-(1-methylbenzimidazol-2-yl)-2-propylbenzimidazol-1-yl]methyl]phenyl]benzoic acid.

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Structure of telmisartan given in figure1:

HYDROCHLOROTHIAZIDE

Hydrochlorothiazide is a thiazide-type diuretic and antihypertensive medication widely used to manage hypertension (high blood pressure) and edema (fluid retention) associated with conditions such as congestive heart failure, liver disease, and renal disorders. It acts primarily in the distal convoluted tubules of the kidney by inhibiting the sodium-chloride cotransporter, thereby reducing reabsorption of sodium and chloride, increasing urinary excretion of sodium, chloride and water, and ultimately lowering blood volume and blood pressure. Hydrochlorothiazide may be used alone or in combination with other antihypertensive agents to enhance blood pressure control.

Chemical formula: C₇H₈ClN₃O₄S₂

Molecular weight: 297.7 g/mol

IUPAC Name: 6-chloro-1,1-dioxo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1λ6,2,4-Benzothiadiazine- 7-sulfonamide.

Structure of hydrochlorothiazide given in figure2:

MATERIALS AND METHODS

CHEMICAL AND REAGENTS

Standard samples of telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide were purchased from dharmtech ltd, navi Mumbai, India. Potassium bromide (IR grade) was obtained from AKCP, viruthu nagar, India.

FTIR INSTRUMENTATION

The FTIR analyses were carried out using shimadzu IR tracer-100 FTIR Spectrophotometer. FTIR spectra were recorded in the wave no range between 4000-400 cm⁻¹ averaging 45 scans per sample using an ominal resolution of 8cm⁻¹ employing background spectrum of KBr. The IR solution PC software was used for data acquisition, processing & spectral analysis.

Solid sampling technique of FTIR using pressed pellet technique

Steps of KBr with sample pressed pellet formation

Shimadzu IR Tracer-100-FTIR spectrophotometer

PREPARATION OF WORKING STANDARD

Accurately weighed Telmisartan (10mg) was mixed with 990mg of KBr as diluents and further

diluted to make a concentration of 1 % w/w of Telmisartan.

SELECTION OF ANALYTICAL WAVENUMBER

Working standard (1% w/w) of pure drug that is Telmisartan was scanned in the IR range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹ with resolution of 8 and 45 scans. Wavenumber (intensity) parameter is select for pure drug in such a way that one can select

wavenumber in a range. Functional group selected for Telmisartan is carbonyl group, N-H group and O-H group wave number found in range of 1715-1730 cm⁻¹, 3500-3700 cm⁻¹ & 3300-3400 cm⁻¹ IR spectrum of Telmisartan is shown in figure 1

Figure 1: FTIR spectrum of Telmisartan

	Peak	Intensity	Corr. Intensity	Base (H)	Base (L)	Area	Corr. Area
1	530.42	93.26	5.30	557.43	491.85	289.052	196.852
2	648.08	90.73	7.29	688.59	611.43	451.121	297.271
3	746.45	14.19	83.79	806.25	688.59	4508.546	4270.592
4	862.18	71.19	27.31	908.47	806.25	1429.075	1273.369
5	935.48	93.90	4.74	962.48	908.47	191.474	118.241
6	1012.63	76.98	21.49	1066.64	962.48	1239.872	1080.192
7	1122.57	67.94	30.25	1170.79	1066.64	1680.025	1492.883
8	1259.52	12.12	86.16	1359.82	1170.79	9198.666	8876.234
9	1452.40	10.00	88.16	1554.63	1359.82	9272.851	8911.018
10	1598.99	81.88	16.41	1633.71	1562.34	735.607	612.916
11	1695.43	13.28	85.21	1770.65	1633.71	5215.278	5007.065
12	1905.67	87.25	12.07	2000.18	1770.65	1429.447	1238.683
13	2308.79	94.55	2.88	2343.51	2266.36	308.959	110.892
14	2459.24	85.43	11.91	2547.97	2343.51	1982.196	1439.973
15	2592.33	94.53	3.42	2646.34	2547.97	365.583	170.766
16	2750.49	90.75	6.97	2835.36	2673.34	947.003	577.283
17	2875.86	89.53	8.47	2914.44	2835.36	494.274	335.807
18	2960.73	75.15	22.96	3003.17	2914.44	1185.445	1018.886
19	3051.39	74.33	23.82	3107.32	3003.17	1395.306	1204.700
20	3387.00	90.62	7.11	3498.87	3250.05	1386.900	832.094
21	3637.75	94.98	3.00	3693.68	3529.73	618.243	256.982
22	3741.90	93.08	5.02	3786.27	3693.68	393.008	218.826
23	3853.77	95.49	2.42	3898.14	3792.05	373.479	152.012

PREPARATION OF WORKING STANDARD

Accurately weighed hydrochlorothiazide (10 mg) was mixed with 990 mg of KBr as diluent and further diluted to make a concentration of 1 % w/w of hydrochlorothiazide.

SELECTION OF ANALYTICAL WAVENUMBER

Working standard (1% w/w) of pure drug that is hydrochlorothiazide was scanned in the IR range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹ with resolution of 8 and 45 scans. Wavenumber (intensity) parameter is select for pure drug in such a way that one can select wavenumber in a range. Functional group selected for hydrochlorothiazide is O=S=O (Sulphone), N-H group wavenumber found in range of 1132-1159 cm⁻¹ & 3500-3700 cm⁻¹ IR spectrum of hydrochlorothiazide is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: FTIR spectrum of hydrochlorothiazide

	Peak	Intensity	Corr. Intensity	Base (H)	Base (L)	Area	Corr. Area
1	457.13	78.75	20.07	499.56	403.12	1088.986	970.819
2	536.21	78.10	21.23	572.86	499.56	855.829	806.813
3	611.43	79.17	19.83	653.87	578.64	789.380	713.610
4	678.94	92.49	6.15	713.66	653.87	250.931	166.291
5	769.60	48.02	50.67	817.82	713.66	2986.172	2846.917
6	860.25	83.58	14.97	891.11	825.53	611.847	518.627
7	931.62	73.83	24.89	972.12	891.11	1229.459	1125.958
8	1047.35	54.22	45.07	1095.57	983.70	2787.089	2708.176
9	1165.00	18.75	80.50	1226.73	1095.57	5598.327	5500.156
10	1327.03	10.00	89.00	1408.04	1230.58	7597.176	7421.828
11	1436.97	93.22	5.61	1467.83	1408.04	252.161	182.160
12	1523.76	62.51	36.95	1564.27	1475.54	1725.675	1681.549
13	1610.56	31.61	67.74	1672.28	1564.27	3632.883	3569.071
14	1805.37	93.06	6.12	1897.95	1743.65	493.102	379.293
15	2318.44	95.65	3.29	2414.88	2262.50	396.943	264.391
16	2580.76	95.14	3.83	2634.76	2526.75	316.421	205.961
17	2831.50	82.89	16.47	2922.16	2781.35	1106.745	1028.064
18	2953.02	95.35	3.45	2987.74	2922.16	202.814	119.860
19	3068.75	95.07	2.53	3109.25	3008.95	373.777	125.482
20	3167.12	68.90	29.65	3221.12	3109.25	1821.291	1655.868
21	3269.34	79.10	20.01	3313.71	3221.12	1037.425	956.038
22	3385.07	38.22	60.96	3475.73	3313.71	5357.859	5227.598
23	3610.74	95.55	3.26	3691.75	3493.09	553.980	314.128
24	3738.05	96.26	2.78	3786.27	3691.75	217.229	127.275

METHOD OF VALIDATION

The developed method was validated as per literature available and ICH guidelines by studying the following method validation parameters.

ACCURACY

The accuracy of the developed method evaluated by standard addition method with recovery of pure drug at 3 different quantities (75, 100 and 125 % w/w). To the pre analyzed tablet powder of Telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide, the known amount of Telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide

studied. Powder corresponds to 75, 100 and 125 % w/w of label claim was added.

Recovery study was performed by 75, 100 and 125 % w/w of working standard to a pre-analyzed sample and the final diluted solutions prepared in such a way that their concentrations should be in linearity range and percentage amount recovered calculated accordingly. The sample was mixed thoroughly and analyzed by making appropriately 1 % w/w dilutions with potassium bromide powder in three replicates. Peak area of this mixture was measured in the range of 1132-1159 cm⁻¹ using KBr as blank for background is shown in the table 1.

Table1: Recovery studies at a for drugs Telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide

Drug	Recovery level	Conc of Sample (microgram/ml)	Conc of standard added (microgram/ml)	Conc recovered (microgram/ml)	% Recovery	Mean / % RSD
TEL	75%	100	50	150.25	100.16	100.22/ 0.4626
	100%	150	50	199.60	99.8	
	125%	200	50	251.80	100.72	
HCTZ	75%	50	25	75.9	100.48	100.48/ 0.0507
	100%	75	25	100.44	100.44	
	125%	100	25	125.68	100.54	

PRECISION

The precision of the method was evaluated by inter-day and intraday variation studies. In intraday studies working dilutions of sample were analyzed triplicate in a day and percentage relative

standard deviation (%RSD) was calculated. In the inter-day variation studies, working dilutions of sample were analyzed on three consecutive days and percentage relative standard deviation (% RSD) was calculated shown in table 2.

Table 2 : Intra-day and Inter-day precision

Intraday precision	Conc (micro gram/ml)	Mean con (microgram/ ml) ± SD	% RSD	Inter day Precision	Conc (micro gram/ml)	Mean conc (microgram/ ml) ±SD	% RSD
Telmisartan	4	4.0003±0.0100	0.2504	Telmisartan	4	3.9966±0.0230	0.5778
	12	1.120337±0.0663	0.5512		12	11.9533±0.0602	0.5042
	18	18.0567±0.0378	0.2096		18	17.9737±0.0553	0.3077
HCTZ	8	8.012±0.0081	0.1021	HCTZ	8	7.9366±0.0503	0.6341
	12	12.0566±0.0585	0.4859		12	11.8967±0.0602	0.5066
	16	15.99±0.1562	0.9768		16	15.8400±0.0458	0.2893

ANALYSIS OF MARKETED TABLET FORMULATION

Accurately weighed 20 tablets (i.e, Telma H) and average weight were determined. Powder weight equivalent to 40mg of Telmisartan and 12.5mg of

hydrochlorothiazide were taken and mixed with KBr and further diluted to 1% w/w concentration. Peak of these dilutions were measured in the range 1132-1159cm⁻¹ using KBr as blank is shown in the table 3 and figure 3.

Table 3: Analysis data for Telma H using FTIR method

Label claim	Amount (mg) per tablet (label claim)	Amount found (mg) (mean value)	Label claim % (mean value)	Standard deviation (SD)	% RSD
TEL	40mg	39.66 mg	99.15%	0.89	0.25-0.55%
HCTZ	12.5mg	12.49 mg	99.98%	0.88	0.10-0.97%

Figure3:FTIR spectrum ofTelma H

	Peak	Intensity	Corr. Intensity	Base (H)	Base (L)	Area	Corr. Area
1	453.27	79.67	15.08	507.28	403.12	1307.676	773.505
2	549.71	87.66	9.43	582.50	507.28	599.324	389.559
3	624.94	86.43	9.60	663.51	582.50	744.002	423.022
4	700.16	90.08	5.22	729.09	663.51	475.621	170.974
5	775.38	37.20	57.97	825.53	729.09	3403.729	2938.554
6	875.68	36.20	60.38	937.40	833.25	3080.929	2740.833
7	1008.77	33.19	61.25	1051.20	956.69	3599.972	3072.697
8	1089.78	64.16	29.90	1134.14	1051.20	1788.781	1292.148
9	1274.95	66.40	28.91	1344.38	1220.94	2387.574	1808.045
10	1427.32	10.00	85.57	1523.76	1344.38	8457.321	7667.539
11	1564.27	89.37	7.38	1614.42	1523.76	663.714	376.446
12	1666.50	52.12	45.10	1739.79	1614.42	2907.779	2547.470
13	1899.88	90.55	4.09	1948.10	1859.38	652.571	175.268
14	2061.90	89.81	6.91	2110.12	2004.04	714.433	354.580
15	2150.63	94.58	3.12	2222.00	2110.12	446.185	179.303
16	2322.29	85.18	11.35	2418.74	2264.43	1484.382	944.919
17	2513.25	84.82	11.41	2584.61	2418.74	1517.067	895.608
18	2661.77	69.10	26.70	2767.85	2590.40	3358.808	2604.028
19	2897.08	17.91	77.49	3005.10	2767.85	9285.446	8195.452
20	3170.97	81.74	9.56	3228.84	3126.61	1497.095	635.430
21	3282.84	88.68	5.98	3356.14	3228.84	1038.580	382.320
22	3408.22	74.36	22.00	3489.23	3356.14	2112.208	1636.641
23	3541.31	64.08	33.52	3687.90	3489.23	3268.398	2945.164
24	3743.83	92.57	4.19	3772.76	3687.90	411.223	202.378

RECOVERY STUDIES

To check the accuracy of the developed method and to study the interference of formulation additives, analytical recovery experiments were carried out by standard addition method at 75% 100% and 125% level. From the total carried amount of drug found the % recovery was calculated.

Drug	Level of addition	% recovery
Telmisartan	75%	100.16
	100%	99.8
	125%	100.72
Hydrochlorothiazide	75%	100.48
	100%	100.44
	125%	100.54

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The new FTIR method was developed for quantization of Telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide in tablet formulation by using a solid sampling technique. The IR spectra of standard Telmisartan & hydrochlorothiazide obtained by pressed pellet technique using KBr in figure 1 & figure 2. To identification of functional groups in raw materials.

IR spectrum of Telmisartan showed peaks at 1695.45 cm^{-1} , 3387.00 cm^{-1} , & 3637.75 cm^{-1} corresponding to carbonyl group, O-H group, N-H group respectively. Hydrochlorothiazide IR spectrum gave peaks at 3269.34 cm^{-1} , 1327.03 cm^{-1} & 1165.00 cm^{-1} corresponding to N-H group, SO^2 asymmetric stretching, SO^2 symmetric stretching respectively.

The marketed tablet formulation that is TelmaH was analyzed using developed method & the results of analysis are shown in table 3. The average recovery of Telma H was 100% w/w of label claim & the % RSD value was 0.25-0.55% & 0.10-0.97% (< 2%).

CONCLUSION

Traditionally, FTIR spectrophotometer is employed for the qualitative analysis of pharmaceuticals; however, with advent in sampling techniques, FTIR spectrophotometer may serve as useful technique for qualitative and quantitative analysis of solid-state pharmaceuticals. In the present studies, we report the development and validation of eco-friendly stability indicating FTIR method for the quantification of solid-state Telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide and its successful application to pharmaceuticals. The proposed method was found to be precise, accurate, and suitable for analysis of Telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide as bulk drug and in pharmaceuticals formulation. Thus, the developed method has the advantage of being solvent free,

eco-friendly, cost effective and involving relatively simple sample preparation. The developed validated method, can be useful for the routine quality control analysis of Telmisartan and hydrochlorothiazide in pharmaceuticals industries with desired precise and accuracy.

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HOW TO CITE: Sudha N, Angel J, Ananthi A, Ansar Mohamed Hussain A, Sheik Hussain M, Sornaraj L, Development and Validation of FTIR Method for Telmisartan- Hydrochlorothiazide Tablets, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 3, 2063-2072. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19104650>